

Rigor and Reproducibility Fall 2021

Instructors/Course Directors

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Location:

Zoom Registration:

<https://nyulangone.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJwvcOCqrzggHdcP2THhFcnJTfDp6ooKZAJJ>

Dates: 9/15/21-11/10/21

Time: Wednesdays 3:00-4:30. All times New York Time.

Office Hours:

Mondays at 1:00PM or by appointment

<https://nyulangone.zoom.us/j/96843282631?pwd=MHQyYek9HUUndOMkU0VjBsZlora3lQZz09>

Class Goals

1. Students will be able to describe the role of reproducibility in their research, and explain the ways that study design, analysis, and reporting can contribute to reproducible science
2. Address NIH requirements on assessment of scientific premise by being able to find and appraise existing research
3. Explain and create data documentation plans and computationally reproducible analysis
4. Recognize which key resources need to be authenticated and the role the NYULH cores play in ensuring reproducibility

Learning Objectives

Students will be able to...

1. Outline and describe issues of replicability at each phase of the research process.
2. Appraise an article and identify strengths and weaknesses with regards to rigor and reproducibility.
3. Perform a comprehensive literature search and summarize the relevance of effective searching for rigorous research.
4. Outline the elements of best practices in research data management
5. Outline and explain the elements of computational reproducibility and explain their value.

Expectations

Students are expected to attend all class sessions and submit homework in a timely manner. If you need an extension, please contact the course instructors before the assignment is due to discuss options.

All class assignments must be done in your own words and reflect your own work.

If additional accommodations are needed for reasons including disability, family issues, etc. please let us know or if you prefer contact the department administrators.

Calendar and Class Topics

Date	Time	Class Topic*
9/15/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Replicability, Part 1

9/22/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Replicability, Part 2
9/29/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Search Mechanics
10/6/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Research Data Management
10/13/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Search Appraisal and Mechanics Continuation
10/20/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Authentication of Key Resources
10/27/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Computational Reproducibility, Part 1
11/3/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Computational Reproducibility, Part 2/Emerging Topics
11/10/21	3:00-4:30pm NY Time	Final Assessment

***Order of classes subject to change**

Classes

1. Replicability, Part 1

Class Objectives:

- Be able to articulate the difficulties in assessing replicability
- Understand what is driving concerns about lack of reproducibility/replicability in science
- Understand how ignoring sex as a biological in studies contributes to irreproducibility
- Understand the prevalence and impact of failure to include randomization and blinding in study design

Before class:

Suggested Readings:

- Lithgow GJ, Driscoll M, Phillips P. A long journey to reproducible results. *Nature*. 2017 Aug 22;548(7668):387-388.
<https://www.nature.com/news/a-long-journey-to-reproducible-results-1.22478>
- Yong E. A waste of 1,000 Research Papers. *The Atlantic* 2019 May 17.
<https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2019/05/waste-1000-studies/589684/>

Class Assessment:

Watch this video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a4fUU85ABwc>

Write a reflective paragraph (~200 words) addressing blinding and randomization in your field of research. Questions to consider:

- How is blinding and randomization applied in your field of research? Are there limitations to what can be randomized, and if so why? Do you think there is room for improvement? If you have employed randomization in a study, did you consider all the factors discussed in the video?

2. Replicability, Part 2

Class Objectives:

- Be able to recognize problems with interpreting statistics and how they affect replicability
- Recognize how publication bias may impact the “truth” of what can be learned from publications
- Understand the rationale for preregistration
- Be aware of guidelines and tools that facilitate reproducibility/replicability through transparent reporting
- Know the different components of the NIH Rigor & Reproducibility guidelines

Before class:

Suggested Readings:

- Amrhein V, Greenland S, McShane B. Scientists rise up against statistical significance. *Nature*. 2019 Mar;567(7748):305-307.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-00857-9>
- Ioannidis JPA. The Importance of Predefined Rules and Prespecified Statistical Analyses: Do Not Abandon Significance. *JAMA*. 2019 Apr 4.
<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/2730486>

Class Assessment:

Write a short essay (500 words maximum) on the two types of statistical error discussed in class, and what they mean. Make sure to explain what a p value is and discuss benefits and drawbacks of this metric. In your own work, what are ways you could make clearer when you are conducting exploratory vs. hypothesis testing research? How might you provide context on statistical results in your work?

3. Search Mechanics

Class Objectives:

- Students will be able to articulate how a comprehensive search fulfills NIH requirements on rigor
- Students will be able to construct a comprehensive search that employs:
 - Proper functioning Boolean logic
 - Appropriate syntax for PubMed and additional biomedical literature databases
- Students will be able to explain the benefits and drawbacks of using multiple databases.

Before class:

Suggested Readings:

- Leenaars, M., Hooijmans, C. R., van Veggel, N., ter Riet, G., Leeflang, M., Hooft, L., ... Ritskes-Hoitinga, M. (2012). A step-by-step guide to systematically identify all relevant animal studies. *Laboratory Animals*, 46(1), 24–31. <http://doi.org/10.1258/la.2011.011087>
- Gordon, W. (2019) “6 Google Tricks That Will Turn You Into an Internet Detective” *New York Times*.
https://www.nytimes.com/2019/08/21/smarter-living/6-google-tricks-that-will-turn-you-into-an-internet-detective.html?fallback=0&recId=1PmaNrnACnHIEZiBdNlo9XTArXb&locked=1&geoContinent=NA&geoRegion=PA&recAlloc=home-geo&geoCountry=US&blockId=home-living-vi&imp_id=320560633&action=click&module=Smarter%20Living&pgtype=Homepage

Class Activities:

- Overview of NIH Rigor and Reproducibility as it relates to searching.
- Explanation of Boolean Logic.
- Hands on work in PubMed including work on:
 - Creating synonyms
 - Finding entry terms (MeSH)
 - Correctly formatting Boolean operators
- Hands on work creating a search in Web of Science including work on:
 - Citation networks
- Hands on work in Google Scholar including work on:
 - Searching a specific journal

Class Assessment:

You are interested in the role of BRCA1 in cancer among smokers. Build a thorough search to avoid missing relevant abstracts in PubMed. This should include the use of boolean operators

like AND, OR and NOT; parentheses to group like terms. Provide the string you searched in PubMed and the number of results.

Also answer the following:

- What are places you could look for useful terms?
- If you were getting too many results, what are some ways you could narrow down the search?

4. Research Data Management

Class Objectives:

- Describe the key elements necessary for inclusion in a data management plan
- Apply research data management and documentation best practices to the following stages of the data lifecycle:
 - Data collection
 - Data organization
 - Data storage
 - Data preservation
 - Data sharing
- Articulate the importance of applying research data management best practices to their own research

Before class:

Suggested Readings:

- Schiermeier Q. Data management made simple. Nature. 2018 Mar 15;555(7696):403-405. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-03071-1>
- Everyone needs a data-management plan. Nature. 2018 Mar 15;555(7696):286. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-03065-z>

Class Assessment:

Based on the Schiermeir article and the class slides:

- Write a short essay (500 word maximum) describing three separate measures you could implement to improve your research data management practices currently.
- Explain how and why these three measures are important within:
 - the context of your research,

- within the biomedical research landscape more broadly.

5. Search Appraisal and Mechanics continuation

Class Objectives:

- Students will be able to systematically appraise an article from the literature
- Students will be able to identify tools for critical appraisal of literature
- Students will be able to summarize bias as it relates to published literature

Before class:

Required Readings:

Viudez-Martínez, A, García-Gutiérrez, MS, Manzanares, J. Gender differences in the effects of cannabidiol on ethanol binge drinking in mice. *Addiction Biology*. 2019;e12765. <https://doi-org.ezproxy.med.nyu.edu/10.1111/adb.12765>

Suggested Readings:

Hooijmans CR, Rovers MM, de Vries RB, Leenaars M, Ritskes-Hoitinga M, Langendam MW. SYRCLE's risk of bias tool for animal studies. *BMC medical research methodology*. 2014;14:43. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4230647/>

Krauth D, Woodruff TJ, Bero L. Instruments for assessing risk of bias and other methodological criteria of published animal studies: a systematic review. *Environmental health perspectives*. 2013;121(9):985-92. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3764080/>

Chapter 5 of : Users Guide to Medical Literature

<https://mhebooklibrary-com.ezproxy.med.nyu.edu/doi/book/10.1036/9780071808729?contentTab=true>, page 86-93

Class discusses literature from homework:

- Summarize research question
- Discuss author's affiliations, and any COI
- Discuss study design
- Discuss potential bias in the methods described

- Discuss what information is present or missing to make an article reproducible and rigorous

Class Assessment:

Read: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6893205/>

Write a reflection of potential sources of bias, error, and any replicability issues. What areas of potential bias and reproducibility problems can you identify and why might they create problems? Use the SYRCLE tool (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4230647/>) to appraise and describe your experience. What are pluses and minuses of using an appraisal checklist like SYRCLE?

6. Computational Reproducibility and Intro to R and RStudio for Analysis I

Class Objectives:

- List best practices for computational reproducibility
- Describe the benefits of conducting analysis in a reproducible way
- Be able to create an R Project and connect your project to GitHub

Before class:

Please download both R <https://www.r-project.org/> and R Studio <https://rstudio.com/> to your computer or be prepared to use a classroom laptop. You need to first download R and then download R Studio as the RStudio tool requires the R language . Create a free github account at github.com (if you already have one, no need to create a new one).

Suggested Readings:

- Wilson G, Bryan J, Cranston K, Kitzes J, Nederbragt L, Teal TK. Good enough practices in scientific computing. PLoS computational biology. 2017;13(6):e1005510. <https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005510>

Class Assessment:

Go to https://classroom.github.com/a/cYkF9a_M to accept the homework, then:

- 1) Create an R Project to pull “CompRepro.rmd” file from GitHub.
- 2) In the file, please describe one of the ways that Wilson et. al. suggest is a good practice for computational reproducibility and how a tool like R can be used. Write your answer below.

3) Add a code chunk and find the square root of 4 to the 13th power. If you are unsure of what command to use, google it.

4) Save the file, commit the changes, and push the homework to the GitHub repository for the homework.

7. Authentication of Key Resources

Class Objectives:

- Articulate the difference between key resource and non-key resource
- Be aware of authentication plan resources for:

Antibody validation | Cell line authentication | Purified proteins | Plasmids |
Nucleic Acids | Specialty chemicals | Genetically Modified Animals or Cells

- Describe an authentication plan to identify and validate key resources essential for the experimental design
- Be aware of DART Cores as resource for multidisciplinary research expertise employing best practices for scientific rigor and responsible conduct of research

8. Emerging Topics in Reproducibility

Suggested Reading:

Haibe-Kains B. et al. (2020) "Transparency and Reproducibility in Artificial Intelligence" *Nature*:
https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-020-2766-y.epdf?sharing_token=jUIAW9u9SrgEI80UAgIBN9RgN0jAjWel9jnR3ZoTv0M3qEeZVaYZS89U0ri_i4YleK4XnxaRGmHjiSdAGpc66Fr6avArzr4NCc-zKjkeoAAgXDXeTvYw7RqQscyw9iv2qYNg8-GEd0t_LGJc1xPtHo144hFs3SvZ2sZiy1fCiCY%3D

Class Objectives:

- Be able to identify challenges and issues in emerging topics, like reproducibility of machine learning and AI research.
- Students will be able to identify challenges relating to reproducibility in computational research, both involving and not involving end-users.

9. Final Assessment

An open-book/open-internet final exam will be distributed to students by email. Students must do this work individually and may not work together. We will review class materials that will be on the final in the class before the assessment is distributed.

Evaluation

- Pass/Fail
- Attendance at all classes*
- Completion of all assignments by the due date (the start of the following class)*
- A grade of 70% or higher on assignments and final assessment
- Homework and participation are 60% of the grade, and the final is 40%

*Students who either must miss class or are unable to complete an assignment on time must contact the instructors at hsl.dataservices@nyulangone.org for permission, which is at the professor's discretion.